

A Study on Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience

R.Sriprija

*Student, Department of Computer Science,
New Horizon College, Bengaluru, India*

M.Deepthi

*Student, Department of Computer Science,
New Horizon College, Bengaluru, India*

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Abstract

This article explores the proposition that the brain, normally seen as an organ of the human body, should be understood as a biologically based form of artificial intelligence, in the course of which the case is made for a new kind of 'humanocentrism'. The human brain is the best example of intelligence known, with unsurpassed ability for complex, real-time interaction with a dynamic world. The Artificial Intelligence researchers trying to emulate its remarkable functionality will benefit by gaining an understanding about neuroscience, and the differences between Natural and Artificial Intelligence. AI has an important role to play in research because Artificial Intelligence focuses on the mechanisms that generate intelligence and cognition. Artificial Intelligence can also benefit from studying the neural mechanisms of cognition, because this research can reveal important information about the nature of intelligence and cognition itself. Hybrids of living neural tissue and robots, called hybrot, allow detailed investigation of neural network mechanisms that may inform the future AI. The field of neuroscience will also benefit tremendously from advances in AI, to deal with their massive knowledge bases and help understand Natural Intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Natural Intelligence; Neuroscience; Human Cognition; Brain

Introduction

An alien power plant was pulled out in a South American forest. After cleaning and dusting it off, the archeologists flip the switch on, and it still works! Electricity kept flowing in that power plant without needing any sort of fuel. This particular scenario is completely related to the field of AI. Today we have incredibly capable machines which are extremely efficient and intelligent that consumes less than 100 Watts of electricity. Have you ever imagined what would happen if AI became a little less artificial and more brain-like, it might be a step closer to achieving Natural Intelligence (NI). Imagine Artificial Intelligence was as perfect as humans at fields like speech or reading minds in fractions of seconds or the level of problem analyzing and solving.

How do you think humans are so good at interacting with the real world with zero issues? Well, I'd say thank your complex neural

systems that is inside your brain. Those thousands of nerves connected to each and every corner of your body, that makes your life so simple. Now picturize a world where the AI is directed towards our brains. A fusion of the intelligent brain and an intelligent machine would undoubtedly give you a wonderful output. Don't you think?

The benefits to building Artificial Intelligence of closely examining biological intelligence are two-fold. First, neuroscience i.e., our brain's nervous system provides a rich source of imagination for new types of framework as well as algorithms to the logical and mathematical based methods that are dominating the approaches to AI. Second, neuroscience can practically give the validation and the verification of AI techniques that are already existing. For example, say an algorithm is not reaching the level of expected performance, and we as humans observe the functioning then we are most likely to find a solution to the algorithm and making it work in the given system. But then of course from an engineering point of view, what works is all that matters.

On an average, we could say that artificial intelligence is understood by common men. But not everybody has knowledge on Neuroscience for that matter. To link neuroscience with Artificial Intelligence, it is advisable to take a neuroscience course or read various books related to it. The Society of Neuroscience (SFN) website is a very reliable source for the introductory books, articles and surveys about several neuroscience topics. The SFN consists of over 30,000 neuroscientists who meet up every year and present their latest researches to be up to date.

Objective

The purpose of this study is to show how the future is going to be a new era where the intelligent machines are going to be benefitted by the working of the human brain.

Methodology

Nature of Study

This study concentrates on the descriptive nature of data only. It presents the secondary form of data collected from different resources.

Secondary Data

The secondary data has been put together from various articles, data from different websites, research papers as well as a few journals.

What do we already know about our brain's nervous system that can benefit the AI?

1. The brain is not a digital computer.
“The brain-as-digital-computer” metaphor has proven to be popular and usually is carried way too far. Basically, a neuron's potential is compared to the binary scheme of a biological implementation in the AI field. Such misinterpretations of the brain need to be corrected from our thoughts about artificial intelligence. There are crystal clear differences between a computer and a brain.

The differences are as follows

1. Brains don't have a Central Processing Unit

The processing capabilities of a brain are diverse and distributed all over the brain. It does not have or need a 'unit' for processing anything. The brain processes information by interacting with other areas of the nervous system.

2. No need of Memory Management Systems

A computer's memory consists of RAM, hard disks and pendrives which are used to store

information and are said to be efficient too. But a brain activates a region while perceiving or recalling a memory. They involve a fluctuation of the one of the neural membranes. The human brain REMEMBERS concepts unlike the computer intelligence.

3. **Natural Intelligence uses Lots of Sensors**

The major differences between NI and AI is the number of sensors that an animal possess without any requirement of algorithms or codes. The human brain, is extremely good at making the best use of whatever sense data is available. Even blind people without much training or support travel places to places only by paying attention to the sounds around them. AI could actually adopt designs of the working of a human brain to visibly increase strong real-time control on machines.

4. **What we do not know about how the brain works**

In order to implement NI on AI, there are certain things we must know about how brains work such as:

How do biological networks truly work? The neurons and glial cells both store and process information in a distributed manner. Glial cells provide support to the neurons and give insulation between them. Glial cells are the richest cell types in the central nervous system. According to the neurobiologists, the memory stored are changed in the physical structure of brain cells.

Emerging Tools for Neuroscience

A hybrid robot, commonly termed as hybrot is an artificial intelligence organism in the form of a robot manipulated by the computer which consists of both electronic and biological aspects. Hybrot can also be thought as a “semi-living”, a term used by the inventors of hybrot.

Neurally controlled simulated animals are a living neuronal network anatomical twists and dynamics of the real brain functioning. Unlike with those of the real animals, the brain can stay extremely still on the microscope sphere when the body is behaving. To picturize the morphological coordinates of learning while it happens, a custom multiphoton microscope is built.

These living neurons are made on a multi-electrode array (MEA) which is used for recording and simulation of cultured neuronal networks. The hybrid robots are equipped with sensory systems. By learning topics such as embodied cultured networks with tools like MEA, we may also learn some new and interesting aspects of dynamics, memory storage and sensory processing that could be used to take AI one step closer to NI.

A benefit of the hybrot approach is that sensory- motor mappings can be created. Every cultured network including MEA culture shows a robust network phenomenon of short term hiving and unmanageable period : the net’s response to the time of two-stimuli is raised when the stimuli are less than 30ms apart, while the response is downcasted if they are 100-500ms apart.

Neuroscience to Artificial Intelligence and Back Again

Artificial neural network that are currently being inspired biologically that are trying to elucidate brain networks are slowly teaming with the experimental neuroscience. The fields of Cognitive Science has made immense progress using theoretical foundations having no basis in neuroscience. Cognitive Science basically means the study of human mind and everything it does. To understand how the brain works, neuroscience and cognitive science are both helpful. I think its time for the world’s best technology, Artificial Intelligence to progress in the direction of the brain. This could

also involve PhD programs that combine neuroscience and AI.

In fact both sides, i.e., AI and neuroscience need to travel across the boundary and learn what the other could offer. How can neuroscience benefit from AI?

As we have researched, we now know that the brain is way too complicated for anybody to understand at this point of time. And if it collaborates with AI, new tools and techniques can be discovered to assemble the mass of neuroscience results and come up with better connections and theoretical principles. Once the synergy between AI and neuroscience is increased, more research on neuroscience would inform AI, and better AI could provide neuroscience with tools to interpret the discoveries that they have made.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence has taken high leaps in terms of the degree of challenge it can accomplish. But regardless of all the high-performance developments around AI, it still hasn't reached the boundary of super intelligent AI as of now. AI lacks in abilities such as common sense, human intelligence, instincts in general. And what could possibly be better than reproducing human brain to create “intelligence”.

AI researchers and experts from across the world firmly agree that the collaboration between AI and neuroscience can construct a perfect understanding of the procedures in the brain that can lead to human cognition.

There cannot be any contradictions on the fact that for Artificial Intelligence to advance and develop beyond its current state, it has to achieve some intelligence as complicated as that of humans. And for that, the AI and neuroscience experts will have to work together to produce magnificent results.

Nevertheless, researchers believe that these challenges would inspire to swim deep into the field and construct lifelong learning systems which is pretty close to what the human brain is.

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